

Evaluation Analysis of Stunting Prevention Program in Wonosari Public Health Center, Malang Regency

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Abstract

Introduction: The incidence of short toddlers or commonly referred to as stunting is one of the nutritional problems experienced by toddlers in the world today. Stunting is a major nutritional problem that will have an impact on social and economic life in the community. In Indonesia, it is estimated that 7.8 million children are stunted, and the position of Indonesia is in the top 5 countries with a high number of children experiencing stunting. Therefore, stunting prevention must be carried out seriously. **Purpose:** This study aims to campaign especially for pregnant women to avoid stunting cases. The outreach activities went well and smoothly. The counseling targets aim to gain additional knowledge and awareness about the prevention of stunting itself. **Methods:** The stunting-themed activity was carried out during Ante Natal Care material at the Sumber Tempur village's Polindes. **Results:** there are still many visitors who do not understand what the dangers of stunting are and the dangers that will be obtained in the future. **Conclusion:** This activity needs to be used as a program that is routinely carried out in the long term to change public understanding of stunting prevention and awareness for routine and periodic health checks to prevent certain diseases.

Keywords: *Stunting, Prevention, Puskesmas, Polindes, Health Promotion*

INTRODUCTION

Overcoming health problems is still a serious challenge in Indonesia. One of the health problems that are still high in cases in Indonesia is stunting. The incidence of short toddlers or commonly referred to as stunting is one of the nutritional problems experienced by toddlers in the world today. According to several studies, the incidence of stunting in children is a cumulative process that occurs during pregnancy, childhood, and throughout the life cycle. Currently in the process of stunting in children and the chance of increasing stunting occurs in the first 2 years of life.

Children who experience inhibition in growth due to lack of adequate food intake and recurrent infectious diseases increased metabolic needs, and reduced appetite, resulting in increased malnutrition in children. This

situation makes it more difficult to overcome growth disorders which ultimately have the opportunity for stunting. Stunting is a major nutritional problem that will have an impact on social and economic life in the community. There is clear evidence that stunted individuals have higher rates of death from various causes and an increased incidence of disease. Stunting will affect physical work performance and mental and intellectual function will be disturbed (Mann and Truswell, 2002). This is also supported by Jackson and Calder (2004) who state that stunting is associated with impaired immune function and increases the risk of death. In Indonesia, it is estimated that 7.8 million children are stunted, this data is based on a report issued by UNICEF and positions Indonesia in the top 5 countries with a high number of children experiencing

stunting (UNICEF, 2007). The results of Basic Health Research of the Indonesian Ministry of Health in 2010, nationally, the prevalence of stunting in children aged 2-5 years in Indonesia is 35.6%, consisting of 15.1% very short and 20% short.

Maternal nutritional factors before and during pregnancy are indirect causes that contribute to fetal growth and development. Pregnant women with malnutrition will cause the fetus to experience intrauterine growth retardation (IUGR) so that the baby will be born with malnutrition, and experience growth and development disorders. To achieve this, the government has set stunting as one of the priority programs. Based on the Regulation of the Minister of Health Number 39 of 2016 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of a Healthy Indonesia Program with a Family Approach, the efforts made to reduce the prevalence of stunting include the following, namely: First, Pregnant and Maternity Mothers consist of Interventions in the first 1,000 days of life, Strive for antenatal quality assurance integrated care (ANC), Improving deliveries in health facilities, Organizing high-calorie, protein, and micronutrient (TKPM) feeding programs, Early detection of diseases (communicable and non-communicable), worms eradication, Improving the transformation of Cards to Health (KMS) into MCH handbook, Organizing Early Initiation of Breastfeeding (IMD) counseling and exclusive breastfeeding; and Counseling and family planning services. The second is the target for Toddlers, which consists of monitoring the growth of toddlers, Organizing Supplementary Feeding (PMT) activities for toddlers, Organizing early stimulation of child development; and Providing optimal health services. The third is School Age Children, which consists of Revitalizing School Health Business (UKS), Strengthening the UKS Guidance Team Institution; Organizing

the School Children's Nutrition Program (PROGAS), and Treating schools as smoking and drug-free areas. Fourth, consisting of increasing counseling for clean and healthy living behavior (PHBS), balanced nutrition patterns, not smoking, and consuming drugs; and reproductive health education. Lastly, for Young Adults, it consists of counseling and family planning services (KB), early detection of diseases (infectious and non-communicable); Improving counseling for PHBS, balanced nutrition pattern, and not smoking/consuming drugs.

Stunting prevention is a national priority for the Indonesian government. Priority programs in stunting prevention include accelerating poverty reduction, improving public health and nutrition services, equitable distribution of quality education services, increasing access to decent housing and settlements, and improving basic service governance. Stunting prevention is also an effort to be able to take advantage of the demographic bonus based on population projections in 2035. Currently, there are still many Indonesian children under five who experience stunting, so in the next fifteen years, the Indonesian people will have unproductive human resources, and the demographic bonus cannot be utilized optimally. Therefore, stunting prevention must be carried out seriously. Stunting prevention investments need to be made early on to ensure that Indonesian human resources in the future are of high quality and highly competitive.

METHODS

This Stunting-themed activity was carried out during Ante Natal Care material at the Sumber Tempur village's Polindes. This activity aims to campaign especially for pregnant women to avoid stunting cases. Stunting campaign activities are carried out by providing counseling, especially to pregnant women.

Extension media in the form of power points that promote important points that need to be made efforts to create prevention of stunting especially for pregnant women.

The counseling activities were carried out by young doctors on duty at the Wonosari Health Center assisted by health workers from the Puskesmas who held the public health program. The young doctor gave material with power points to each visitor and explained in more detail in layman's language to the Polindes visitors so that they better understand the meaning and purpose of stunting prevention themselves. In addition, there is also an interaction between young doctors and visitors so that information transfer occurs and makes visitors more motivated to help realize the Stunting goal, which is to prevent babies from failing to grow and develop, such as the stunting category.

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The activity is scheduled for December 30, 2019, from 08.00 WIB to 10.00 WIB. We provide educational

materials to pregnant women who are conducting Ante Natal Care examinations at the Polindes. Delivery of counseling materials using power points that contain the definition of stunting, the causes of stunting consist of four points, namely poor care, limited health services (including ANC services and postnatal care), and lack of access to nutritious food, lack of access to clean water and sanitation. In addition, we also provide materials for the prevention of stunting, namely monitoring the growth of toddlers at the Posyandu, providing clean water and sanitation facilities, keeping the environment clean, meeting the nutritional needs of pregnant women, and giving exclusive breastfeeding until the age of 6 months. In this counseling, it is emphasized to pregnant women by preventing 1000 HPK (First Day of Life) by improving nutrition & health of pregnant women, preventing chronic energy deficiency in pregnant women, and getting blood-added tablets. The young doctor explained using language that was easily understood by the polindes visitors and was allowed to ask questions regarding the material presented. During the counseling, visitors listened to the material delivered by the young doctor in a conducive and enthusiastic manner. Many of the visitors provided feedback in the form of questions related to stunting prevention. After the counseling session was over, it was followed by a group photo between the young doctor and visitors in the polindes as a form of support for stunting prevention and commitment to stunting prevention for pregnant women.

RESULT

The outreach activities went well and smoothly. During the activity, the Polindes visitors paid close attention to the explanation from the young doctor, which was conducive and enthusiastic. After giving the material, the young doctor allowed visitors to ask questions related to

the Stunting material presented, quite a lot of visitors asked and provided feedback related to this stunting counseling activity.

The counseling targets aim to gain additional knowledge and awareness about the prevention of stunting itself. In addition, visitors are expected to be able to avoid risk factors that can trigger the emergence of toddlers with stunting from the womb by changing a healthier lifestyle and maintaining a healthy environment as well.

The target is that the community understands and understands the material so that they can create a healthier life during pregnancy. This can reduce the number of children under five with stunting. In addition, a healthy lifestyle such as a clean and healthy environment can reduce government and private budgets for treatment when sick. There are still many visitors who do not understand what the dangers of stunting are and the dangers that will be obtained in the future. The lack of knowledge and awareness of the importance of healthy living behavior is evident from the number of visitors who come to check themselves only when they are sick. Visitors still lack awareness of the importance of prevention rather than cure. They only realized to check themselves when they were sick. Very few visitors come for regular health checks.

The problems found in this program are some sentences in the material use medical/foreign languages which are too difficult to understand for visitors, most of the visitors still underestimate the dangers of stunting in the future for children's growth, the low level of public knowledge about healthy living behavior patterns and maintaining a clean living environment to avoid stunting in toddlers, and the community stigmatizes that they come to the health service center only when there are complaints about the illness they are experiencing, but there is a very low desire

to do regular health checks before the onset of illness, especially for the elderly.

The plus points of this program are the material provided can increase the knowledge of Polindes visitors about Stunting, namely healthy living behaviors such as improving nutrition and health of pregnant women, preventing energy deficiency in pregnant women, getting blood-added tablets, and keeping the environment clean; the material was delivered by a young doctor in layman's language and was easy to understand so that the information provided could be conveyed properly to the Polindes visitors; direct and two-way interaction between visitors and young doctors so that feedback can be obtained directly from the transfer of information and knowledge; the closed counseling room in the polindes room makes all visitors know if stunting-related counseling is being carried out so that more focused material is given; there is printed media in the form of power points that support young doctors in delivering material related to stunting which is important to increase knowledge about stunting.

And the minus points of this program are not all young doctors can speak Javanese so some visitors have difficulty understanding the stunting material presented; the extension room is not spacious enough so that it is not possible if further counseling to be carried out to more Polindes visitors; and lack of concrete evidence that can evaluate that people are changing their lifestyle and need a long-term evaluation to realize stunting itself.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

This activity needs to be used as a program that is routinely carried out in the long term to change public understanding of stunting prevention and awareness for routine and periodic health checks to prevent certain diseases. It is hoped that a sustainable program, can reduce the

number of children under five with stunting and prevent complications that may be obtained in the future, especially in the Wonosari District community to reduce the personal and government burden of medical expenses incurred in the event of illness.

The short-term solutions for this program are for young doctors to be accompanied by the patient's family or to ask colleagues to translate Indonesian into Javanese so that visitors can more easily understand the material presented and the presenter must provide a wider room such as a special health center counseling room to provide materials related to stunting education. And the long-term solutions for this program are it requires a strong commitment by health workers to provide information on a healthy lifestyle regularly or regularly and Puskesmas need to make sustainable programs related to a community commitment to change their behavior to healthier behavior and need to carry out regular health checks periodically every trimester to the nearest health service center such as Puskesmas and check post-natal care.

REFERENCES

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